

TECHNOLOGIES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF INNOVATIVE COMPETENCE OF FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract. *The relevance of the article is determined by the need to form innovative abilities in future elementary school teachers, to prepare them for the implementation of innovative activities. It is highlighted that one of the urgent pedagogical problems is the training of innovative competent teachers who are able to carry out their professional activities using the necessary effective educational tools and innovations in education.*

Keywords: *innovation, technology, competence, innovative process, innovative education, technical means, competence, modern education, lifelong learning, SMART technology.*

In the world, scientific and research work is being carried out on the issues of expanding the possibility of forming the innovative competence of future primary school teachers, the wide use of information and communication technology tools in the system, and the development of creative models of the pedagogical process aimed at the formation of innovative competence. Also, revealing the motivational effect of encouraging pedagogical features such as inquisitiveness, ingenuity, and research in preparing future primary school teachers for the formation of their innovative competence is of urgent importance.

The development of the education system in our country is characterized by the increasing role of innovative technologies in teaching, it is recognized as an urgent problem to direct future specialists to innovative activities, activate their motivation for quality education, reconsider the place and role of innovative activities in educational institutions, to forecast the process of implementation of educational reforms in accordance with the priority directions of socio-economic development of the regions.

Today, the process of globalization requires the training of competitive, inquisitive and competent personnel according to its social and cultural essence. The use of innovative technologies in the educational process increases the quality of education and students' interest in the profession, and increases the effectiveness of pedagogues in their work. In this place, our president Sh. Mirziyoyev's thoughts "We will mobilize all the strength and capabilities of our state and society so that our young people are independent thinkers, have high intellectual and spiritual potential, and become people who are not inferior to their peers in any field in the world, and become happy" directly correspond to the purpose and mission of our work.

In the pedagogical literature, the terms "Innovative education", "Innovative process" and "Innovative activity" were rarely observed in the recent past. The concept of "innovative education" was first used in 1979 at the "Club of Rome". At the core of this word is the complex

activity of organizing innovations in education, their assimilation, use of innovations and their manifestation.

Innovative education is education that creates an opportunity to create new thoughts, ideas, norms, rules in the learner, to develop qualities and skills related to the natural acceptance of advanced ideas, norms, rules created by other people. The technologies used in the process of innovative education are called educational innovations or innovative educational technologies.

Educational innovations are forms, methods, technologies that are used to solve existing problems in the field of education or in the educational process based on a new approach and achieve more effective results than before.

The innovative process in the field of education is innovation and changes in the concept of education, curriculum, methods of education and training, methodology and styles. The problem of the pedagogue's learning, generalization and popularization of advanced pedagogical experiences and practical implementation of the achievements of pedagogical sciences lies in the original meaning of the word innovative processes in the field of education.

"Competence" and "adequacy" are different concepts: **competence** –is a general description of the specialist's professionalism, regardless of his personal qualities. It exists separately from its official bearer and needs to be possessed. **Adequacy** is personally acquired competence, expression of "person in profession".

By **innovative competence**, we understand a certain level of manifestation of the personal and professional skills of the pedagogue in his innovative activity. In other words, innovative competence is the result of the theoretical and practical preparation of the pedagogue for the implementation of professional activities using educational and effective innovations.

Currently, the use of SMART technologies in the educational process gives effective results. SMART (smart, intelligent, technological) is an acronym, which is essentially a new educational environment. First used by Paul J. Meyer in 1965 and then by George T. Doran in 1981, SMART empowers teachers, professionals, and students to use global knowledge and move from passive content to active content, that is, to combine educational activities.

The advantages of using SMART technology in the educational process for teachers and students are as follows:

- An innovative approach to the presentation of educational material;
- Quick feedback with students;
- Forming a unified real and virtual world;
- Maximum variety of multimedia;
- General information educational environment;
- The large number of information receiving sources;
- Easy management of the educational process;
- Quickly and easily determine the ability of students according to their needs and level;
- Possibility to establish cooperation relations with several educational institutions and create a network for information exchange;
- Rapid feedback with increasing speed and quality of education;
- Development of creativity and opportunities for independent implementation;
- Ability to get necessary information in conditions independent of location and time;
- The ability to start learning for preparation in any situation.

To implement SMART-education, first of all, high-speed Internet that provides maximum mobility to ensure use anywhere, at any time, pedagogues have a mature level of technological competence, automation of the educational process and modern technology is necessary...

In the present period, increasing the efficiency of education, directing the teaching staff to innovative activities, developing the level of professional competence of specialists, applying innovative education and information and communication technologies to the educational process in higher education institutions, mastering and targeted orientation of advanced foreign experiences can be considered as urgent tasks in the higher education system.

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